

Genomics and transcriptomics guided trait stacking of antagonistic mechanisms utilized by *Streptomyces* spp. from underexplored strain collection in SynComs against pathogens causing ash dieback and acute oak decline

Version 1

Description

The project aims to investigate whether an efficient synthetic community inhibiting causal agents of two severely deleterious diseases of broad-leafed trees can be built by combining *Streptomyces* strains using an antimicrobial trait stacking approach. Designed syncoms will be used to target ash dieback and acute oak decline-associated pathogens – *Hymenoscyphus fraxineus*, *Gibbsiella quercinecans*, and *Brenneria goodwinii*. The study will apply genomics and transcriptomics-based assessment of anti-microbial mechanisms represented in underexplored *Streptomyces* strains preserved by the Microbial Strain Collection of Latvia. The most efficient antagonistic combinations of identified anti-microbial mechanisms will be predicted using genomics and metatranscriptomics-based metabolic modeling and validated with wet-lab tests. Results: two scientific publications (submitted to Q1/Q2 journals), two reports at scientific conferences, defended master thesis, new project application, genomics, and metatranscriptomic data deposited in the public data repository. An impact: results will advance fundamental knowledge of arboreal pathology and microbial ecology, and increase accessibility and usability of local microbial resources. Assessment of anti-microbial properties of *Streptomyces* collection of local origin will foster innovations in knowledge-intensive bio-economy – Smart specialization strategy (RIS3) area of Latvia.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

Genomics and transcriptomics guided trait stacking of antagonistic mechanisms utilized by *Streptomyces* spp. from underexplored strain collection in SynComs against pathogens causing ash dieback and acute oak decline (Izp-2024/1-0109)

Researchers

Maris Senkovs (0000-0001-6773-5667)

Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Genomics and transcriptomics guided trait stacking of antagonistic mechanisms utilized by *Streptomyces* spp. from underexplored strain collection in SynComs against pathogens causing ash dieback and acute oak decline

Description:

The project aims to investigate whether an efficient synthetic community inhibiting causal agents of two severely deleterious diseases of broad-leafed trees can be built by combining *Streptomyces* strains using an antimicrobial trait stacking approach. Designed syncoms will be used to target ash dieback and acute oak decline-associated pathogens – *Hymenoscyphus fraxineus*, *Gibbsiella quercinecans*, and *Brenneria goodwinii*. The study will apply genomics and transcriptomics-based assessment of anti-microbial mechanisms represented in underexplored *Streptomyces* strains preserved by the Microbial Strain Collection of Latvia. The most efficient antagonistic combinations of identified anti-microbial mechanisms will be predicted using genomics and metatranscriptomics-based metabolic modeling and validated with wet-lab tests. Results: two scientific publications (submitted to Q1/Q2 journals), two reports at scientific conferences, defended master thesis, new project application, genomics, and metatranscriptomic data deposited in the public data repository. An impact: results will advance fundamental knowledge of arboreal pathology and microbial ecology, and increase accessibility and usability of local microbial resources. Assessment of anti-microbial properties of *Streptomyces* collection of local origin will foster innovations in knowledge-intensive bio-economy – Smart specialization strategy (RIS3) area of Latvia.

Researchers:

[Maris Senkovs \(0000-0001-6773-5667\)](#)

Organizations:

[University of Latvia](#)

Contact: [Senkovs Māris \(maris.senkovs@lu.lv\)](mailto:senkovs.maris@lu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian Council of Science](#)

Grants: Genomics and transcriptomics guided trait stacking of antagonistic mechanisms utilized by *Streptomyces* spp. from underexplored strain collection in SynComs against pathogens causing ash dieback and acute oak decline (Izp-2024/1-0109)

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

Selection of target *Streptomyces* strains.

Selection of target *Streptomyces* strains will be achieved through bioprospecting of 50 uncharacterized historic

Streptomyces strains that are preserved in MSCL-UL. These strains will be tested for in vitro antagonistic activity against

three pathogenic microorganisms - *H. fraxineus*, *G. quercinecans*, *B. goodwinii*. Evaluation of antagonistic properties will

be based on three methodological approaches: 1) agar-plate antagonistic assays - using dual culture and cross-streak

techniques, 2) assessing antagonistic potential of *Streptomyces* conditioned media using agar-well diffusion method, 3)

as well as on liquid co-cultures using high-throughput assay that enables quantitative evaluation of pathogen biomass in

case of *H. fraxineus*. Antagonistic tests against *H. fraxineus* will be performed on a communal medium. Following the

Data Management Plan | Genomics and transcriptomics guided trait stacking of antagonistic mechanisms utilized by *Streptomyces* spp. from underexplored strain collection in SynComs against pathogens causing ash dieback and acute oak decline CC-BY-4.0 DOI: - 04/02/2025

results that will be acquired during dual antagonistic cultures, only the most promising antagonistic Streptomyces/

pathogen pairs will be selected for metatranscriptomic analysis. Six Streptomyces strains will be selected for further

analysis in WP2 and WP3. Our primary aim is to identify Streptomyces strains that exhibit antagonistic properties against

any of the target pathogens and preferably against more than one of the targeted pathogens. Biomass of Streptomyces

and targeted pathogens from single-strain cultures and their dual antagonistic cultures in a liquid medium will be sampled

for subsequent genomic and metatranscriptomic analysis in WP2.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Selection of antagonistic Streptomyces isolates.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- XLS
- JPG

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No!

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Until the end of the project.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Microsoft office

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2028-01-01

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Maris Senkovs (0000-0001-6773-5667)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Powered by

